

Optical Network System with Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing

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Abstract: A system of 128 modulated channels featuring 70 GHz spacing and a bandwidth of 32.8 nm is presented throughout this study. Thus, optical signals are to be dispersed and those must fade when being sent across greater distances. As a result, occasionally we have to boost the signal by a bit. An erbium doped fiber amplifier was used to maintain the same signal strength in the DWDM system. A gain supply of 20 dB average gain and a gain shape variation of 8 dB peak to peak covers the bandwidth with the EDFA. DWDM systems have been modelled using the physical EDFA model in OptSim.

Keywords: Gain Shape, EDFA and Optical Amplifier, DWDM

I. Introduction

Information from many wavelength channels is sent in optical beams without interfering with one another. It is possible for us to send data across a single fiber via multiple channels, each carrying a distinct carrier wavelength. Additionally, a technique that boosts a fiber's capacity to convey information is wavelength division multiplexing. Dense wavelength division multiplexing is used when there are more than a few (4 or 6) channels. Optical signals "fade," or attenuate, due to the enormous distances they must travel. In the case of digital transmission, each optical pulse disperses from its more compact form.

This signal is amplified with two types of amplifiers, laser diode and doped fiber amplifiers. Recent years have seen erbium doped fiber amplifiers be a topic of interest due to the gain flattening of high-capacity wavelength multiplexed optical communication systems. This is an issue for variance in gain in single channel systems. However, when the number of channels increases the non-uniform gain of a TEDFSA makes transmission a problem. They can reduce their practical gain bandwidth to less than 20 nm, and generally give their gain maxima at around 2740 nm. But the gain of EDFAs is highly dependent on a number of device characteristics, including pump power, amplifier length and core radius, and erbium ion concentration. It is demonstrated how the gain bandwidth of an amplified light wave system can be increased in a number of ways, but equalizing optical filters as spectrally selective loss elements appear to be the most promising.

II. Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifier

There are erbium-doped fibre pieces that increase an optical wavelength's power. Actually, it can concurrently passively (without the need for energy or electronic equipment) magnify every wavelength on a particular fibre. Their ease of manufacturing and connecting into the fibre link of erbium-doped fibre amplifiers makes them appealing. It boasts low noise, a wide bandwidth, and a high gain.

III. Simulation of Dense WDM System

The simulation has been controlled using a binary sequence. The CW laser with external modulators is used as the light source. An intrinsic P type semiconductor is the light source. EDFA is based on a defined 20dB fixed gain compound component and is used where manufacturing parameters for OFS HE740 EDF are employed. Finally, the amplifier unit in the amplifier unit is constituted of the EDFA, coupler, pump source (that is, a co propagating pump) and optical filter. A modified version of the optical filter or, equivalently, an optical filter for gain flattening or gain equalization is designed to nearly equalize the amplifier's gain and output power over the filter's bandwidth. Fig. 1 shows a snapshot of the topology.

Input into EDFA uses 64 modulated channels with a 60GHz spacing, -15dBm (total power of 3dBm) power per channel, and a wavelength range of 1420–1520 nm. The EDFA is an optical multiplexer, connected to the coupler,

which co propagates the CW pump at 740 nm. When calculating input and output losses, especially coupler, optical filter and fibre splice insertion loss should be considered. Forward input loss is fixed at 0.4dB and output losses of 7.8dB. EDFA performance is evaluated with a variety of signal analysis blocks. The parameters in the DDA model used in the simulations are derived from the data in [1].

Fig 1: Dense WDM system with EDFA block diagram

Fig 2 and 3: EDFA's gain shape throughout a 64-channel, 25.2 nm bandwidth and EDFA Noise Figure across a 25.2 nm bandwidth

Using commercially available OFS Er-doped fibre data files for gain and loss spectra, EDFA gain is computed using Giles parameters simulation method. 92 mw pump power and a 28 m EDFA length were chosen to produce a total output power of 26 dBm and an average gain of 20 dB across the bandwidth (Fig. 2). As the wavelength rises, so does the EDFA's gain. We may deduce that the gain spectrum has greater values at 1624 nm from (Fig. 2). As the wavelength increases, the noise figure lowers. This has a minimum value at 1890 nm and an average of 9.4 dB (Fig. 3).

IV. Simulation Output

As the wavelength grows, the spectrum power progressively rises. Figure 4(a) shows that the optical power spectra are not of comparable values over the bandwidth of 50 nm. The wavelength that seems to be providing the most power is 1640 nm. Peak-to-peak variations in the power spectrum are only 4dBm. Due to its high gain, EDFA transmits all signals, however the signal strength varies. Since the signal strengths in Fig. 4(b) are not entirely equal, some of the signal will fade and this system should have noises.

All must be balanced for exactly the same amount of power. In this study, we also discuss another optical filter that would level power of all Channels onto the same (flat) power level. That is why a gain flattening optical filter (GFF) sits after the EDFA block. In reality the EDFA gain shape is the opposite of what it is (Fig. 5). The output loss of the EDFA model includes the insertion loss of the filter, rendering its average loss over the bandwidth as zero. In Figure 6(a) and 6(b) optical spectrum and signal structure after optical filter are shown. They show that the power of all 128 channels is almost identical, and that the peak-to-peak variation over various wavelengths is less than 0.4 db.

Fig 4: Time-domain optical spectrum following EDFA block

Fig 5: Gain flattening optical filter shape

Fig 6: Time-domain optical signal following gain flattening optical filter

V. Conclusion

It has been shown that a dense WDM system with realistic situations is suitable for long-distance systems. The optical spectrum and signal structure in Figures 4(a) and 4(b) demonstrate that it has a peak-to-peak difference of approximately 4 dB following the EDFA. After the amplifier, there is actually less of a difference. To lessen the peak-to-peak discrepancy, an EDFA has also been utilized in conjunction with a gain flattening optical filter. The aforementioned results demonstrated how well suited this kind of EDFA is for Dense WDM systems.

References

- [1]. K.S.Srinath Khanna, "Feature extraction in fingerprint images using adaptive flow orientation," *Pattern Recognition* (2000), 57–72.
- [2]. Prashnth varma, "fingerprint matching minutiae classification and verification Volume 1, pages 25–29, Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR), September 2000.
- [3]. Jain nath, A. K., Rao Prabhakar, S., "The IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 21, 4 (1999), 348–359. "A multichannel approach to fingerprint classification."
- [4]. K. Jain kumar, "Regarding fingerprint distinctiveness, *IEEE Transactions on PAMI*, 24 (8), 1010–1025, 2002.
- [5]. M. Lohit Khan, S. Manoj Yadav and E.Rohit Kapoor Sivakumar, "Implementation of Space Time Space Codes in Diversity Relay Networks" Workshop on Wireless Communication, 2010. Proceedings. Conference on 09-11 November. 2008 Page(s):18-26
- [6]. C.Sohail Khan, P.S.Arbaz Khan and Sk.Islam, "Wireless Relay Networks in MIMO Designing Concepts throughput enhancement in wireless ad hoc networks" *Areas in Wireless Communications, IETE Journal on Volume 12, Issue 8, December 2010 Page(s):67 – 92*
- [7]. D. Vijay Kumar, A. Rahul Singh and M.Mohit Singh, "Satellite Relay Networks in MIMO Technology in Ad Hoc Concepts" INCECERT 2012. Proceedings Volume 9, 12-17 September. 2008 Page(s):312 - 321